

Title page

Title In situ observations of halogenated gases at the Shangdianzi background station and emission estimates for northern China

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Abstract

Halogenated gases include ozone-depleting substances and greenhouse gases, such as chlorofluorocarbons, halons, hydrochlorofluorocarbons, hydrofluorocarbons, and perfluorinated gases. In situ atmospheric observations of major halogenated gases were conducted at the Shangdianzi (SDZ) background station, China, from October 2020 to September 2021 using ODS5-pro, a newly developed measurement system. The measurement time series of 36 halogenated gases showed occasional pollution events, where background conditions represented 25% (CH_2Cl_2) to 81% (CF_3Cl , CFC-13) of the measurements. The annual mean background mole fractions of most species at SDZ were consistent with those obtained at the Mace Head station in Ireland. The background conditions were distinguished from pollution events, and the enhanced mole fractions were used to estimate the emissions of four categories of fluorinated gases (F-gases) from northern China using a tracer ratio method. The CO_2 -equivalent (CO_2 -eq) emission of F-gases from northern China reached $181 \pm 18 \text{ Tg yr}^{-1}$ during 2020–2021. Among four categories of F-gases estimated, SF_6 accounted for the highest proportion of CO_2 -eq emissions (24%), followed by HFC-23 (22%), HFC-125 (17%), HFC-134a (13%), NF_3 (10%), CF_4 (5.9%), HFC-143a (3.9%), HFC-32 (3.4%), and HFC-152a (0.2%).

Synopsis The mole fractions of halogenated gases were measured for one year at the Shangdianzi background station. The emissions of four categories of fluorinated gases from northern China were estimated using a tracer ratio method.

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2 **and emission estimates for northern China**

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6 **Abstract**

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8 as chlorofluorocarbons, halons, hydrochlorofluorocarbons, hydrofluorocarbons, and
9 perfluorinated gases. In situ atmospheric observations of major halogenated gases were
10 conducted at the Shangdianzi (SDZ) background station, China, from October 2020 to
11 September 2021 using ODS5-pro, a newly developed measurement system. The
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13 where background conditions represented 25% (CH₂Cl₂) to 81% (CF₃Cl, CFC-13) of
14 the measurements. The annual mean background mole fractions of most species at SDZ
15 were consistent with those obtained at the Mace Head station in Ireland. The
16 background conditions were distinguished from pollution events, and the enhanced
17 mole fractions were used to estimate the emissions of four categories of fluorinated
18 gases (F-gases) from northern China using a tracer ratio method. The CO₂-equivalent
19 (CO₂-eq) emission of F-gases from northern China reached 181 ± 18 Tg yr⁻¹ during
20 2020–2021. Among four categories of F-gases estimated, SF₆ accounted for the highest
21 proportion of CO₂-eq emissions (24%), followed by HFC-23 (22%), HFC-125 (17%),
22 HFC-134a (13%), NF₃ (10%), CF₄ (5.9%), HFC-143a (3.9%), HFC-32 (3.4%), and
23 HFC-152a (0.2%).

24 **Keywords**

25 Halogenated gases; greenhouse gases; in situ measurement; emission; northern
26 China

27 **Synopsis**

28 The mole fractions of halogenated gases were measured for one year at the
29 Shangdianzi background station. The emissions of four categories of fluorinated gases
30 from northern China were estimated using a tracer ratio method.

31 1. Introduction

32 Halogenated gases primarily include chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs),
33 hydrochlorofluorocarbons (HCFCs), hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs), perfluorocarbons
34 (PFCs), halons, nitrogen trifluoride (NF₃), sulfur hexafluoride (SF₆), methyl chloroform
35 (CH₃CCl₃), carbon tetrachloride, and methyl bromide. Under the Montreal Protocol on
36 Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer, hereinafter referred to as Montreal Protocol,
37 production and use of some halogenated gases such as CFCs and halons have been
38 completely phased out as ozone-depleting substances (ODSs) for emissive use globally;
39 HCFCs are currently being phased out.

40 Most halogenated gases are greenhouse gases (GHGs) with high global warming
41 potentials (GWPs). HFCs, the main substitutes for ODSs, have been controlled by both
42 the Kigali Amendment to the Montreal Protocol and the Protocols under the United
43 Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). PFCs, NF₃, and SF₆
44 emitted from the electronics, metal smelting, and electric power industries are also
45 regulated by the UNFCCC owing to their high GWPs. The combined emissions of
46 HFCs have increased in the last two decades and have contributed to global CO₂-
47 equivalent (CO₂-eq) emissions of $1.22 \pm 0.05 \text{ Gt yr}^{-1}$ in 2020, which is comparable to
48 those of CFCs (0.7 Gt yr^{-1}) and HCFCs (0.7 Gt yr^{-1}) combined ¹. Although the global
49 emissions of PFCs are relatively low by mass, their GWPs are extremely high.
50 Furthermore, considering the accelerated growth of NF₃ and SF₆ mole fractions in the
51 atmosphere ¹, the impact of perfluorinated gases on global warming has become
52 increasingly prominent. In 2019, the radiative forcing from halogenated gases had
53 reached 0.41 Wm^{-2} , equivalent to ~19% of the radiative forcing from CO₂ ².
54 Considering their impact on climate change and their low mole fractions, typically
55 measured in parts per trillion (ppt) in the background atmosphere, continuous high-
56 precision observations are necessary.

57 China is one of the countries with the highest emissions of halogenated gases in
58 the world. The emissions of F-gases from China, including HFCs, PFCs, SF₆, and NF₃,
59 which are all potent GHGs, have previously been estimated using atmospheric
60 observations of HFCs ³⁻⁶, PFCs ^{3, 6}, SF₆ ^{7, 8} and NF₃ ⁹. For example, the contributions of
61 aggregated CO₂-eq emissions of the nine most abundant HFCs from China to the global
62 total CO₂-eq emissions increased rapidly from 2.6% to 15% during 2005–2016 ⁴.
63 Studies have been carried out to continuously observe the mole fractions of halogenated

64 gases at both background stations ^{3, 10-12} and urban sites ¹³⁻¹⁶ in China. However, few
65 studies have reported high-precision mole fractions covering a comprehensive range of
66 halogenated gases including NF₃.

67 Northern China, which is densely populated, is one of the most important
68 production bases of fluorine chemical industry ¹⁷, electrolytic aluminum industry ¹⁸ and
69 chlorine alkali industry ¹⁹ in China, leading to a potential key area for halogenated gas
70 emissions. Substantial emissions of important halogenated gases have been shown to
71 originate from northern China (especially from Shandong and Hebei provinces), for
72 example, CFC-11 ²⁰, CH₂Cl₂ ²¹, and HCFC-22 ²². However, only Yao et al., (2012) ³
73 provided quantitative emissions of HFCs and PFCs from northern China in 2010–2011,
74 and there has been no comprehensive and updated estimates for all F-gases emissions
75 from northern China since then.

76 In this study, high-frequency in situ field atmospheric observations at the
77 Shangdianzi (SDZ) background station in northern China were conducted for 36
78 halogenated gases from October 2020 to September 2021, using a newly developed
79 high-precision monitoring system ODS5-pro. The observed data are analyzed to obtain
80 both the background mole fractions and pollution events of 36 halogenated gases, which
81 are presented in section 3.1. Section 3.2 discusses the interspecies correlations between
82 the mole fraction enhancements of halogenated gases. Finally, in section 3.3, a
83 comprehensive emission list of the HCFCs and F-gases from northern China during
84 2020–2021 are estimated based on the observational data, and the results are compared
85 with global emissions to reveal the contribution of HCFCs and F-gases from northern
86 China to the global totals. Information of the ODS5-pro system and its stability
87 verification can be found in the supporting information.

88 **2. Experimental methods**

89 **2.1 Field observation**

90 ODS5-pro, a custom-made system for the in situ observation of halogenated gases,
91 can effectively separate and quantify 36 halogenated gases simultaneously, including
92 individual CFCs, halons, HCFCs, HFCs, PFCs, SF₆, NF₃, CH₃CCl₃, methyl halides, and
93 SO₂F₂. This system is composed of an automatic sampling module, an analysis system,
94 standard gases, auxiliary gases (helium and nitrogen), and data processing systems. The
95 analysis system is composed of a refrigerant-free preconcentration module, a gas
96 chromatography (GC) instrument (A91P, Panna Instruments Co., Ltd., Jiangsu, China),

97 and a quadrupole mass spectrometry (MS) detector (7700B, Suzhou Anyeep Instrument
98 Co., Ltd., Jiangsu, China). The principle and process for the preconcentration module
99 follow the state-of-the-art Medusa GC–MS system, which is widely applied worldwide
100 via the Advanced Global Atmospheric Gases Experiment (AGAGE) ²³. The
101 refrigeration module of ODS5-pro uses a Stirling cooler (TC4189, Shenzhen LIHAN
102 Technology Co., Ltd., Guangdong, China). Information about the sampling and
103 analytical process is detailed in the supporting information S1.1. The system accurately
104 controls the temperature and gas pressure using a self-developed automatic software
105 named ODS Control (Figure S1). The chromatogram from a 2-L sample of ambient air
106 obtained by the ODS5-pro system is shown in Figure S2, and individual chromatograms
107 for 36 species with ambient mole fractions are presented in Figure S3. Good linear MS
108 responses to the sampling volume range of 0.1–4.5L were found for all halogenated
109 gases (Figure S4). The hardware and software of the system are described in the
110 supporting information Section S1.1. The ODS5-pro system showed good performance
111 with precisions of 0.5%, 0.5%–1%, 1%–4% and 4%–11% for species with mole
112 fractions greater than 100, 20–100, 2–20, and 0.1–2 ppt, respectively, as shown in Table
113 S1, which were comparable to Medusa GC-MS system.

114 A one-year field observation at the SDZ background station (40°39' N, 117°07' E,
115 293 m above sea level) was conducted using the ODS5-pro system from October 2020
116 to September 2021. The SDZ station is in a rural area that is 100 km northeast of the
117 Beijing urban area. No industries or populated cities are present within 30 km of the
118 surrounding area. Detailed information of the topography and the impact of the
119 surrounding emission sources can be found in the study by An et al. (2012) ²⁴. A Medusa
120 GC–MS system was also used during the same period for intercomparison of the
121 observation results with those obtained using the ODS5-pro system. The sampling
122 intervals of the ODS5-pro and Medusa GC–MS were 70 min and 65 min, respectively.
123 Data observed by the two systems within a 70 minute interval were paired to compare,
124 as shown in Figure S5, and the comparison is discussed in the supporting information
125 Section S1.4. Further, a cavity ring down spectroscopy system (G2401, Picarro Inc.,
126 Santa Clara, California, USA) was used for the continuous measurement of CO with a
127 measurement precision of <2 parts per billion (ppb). Air samples containing both CO
128 and halogenated gases were collected from the same inlet, and the 5-min mean mole
129 fraction of CO during the halogenated gases sampling time was used for the emission
130 estimates of HFCs and F-gases, as discussed in Section 3.3.

131 2.2 Baseline extraction

132 The baseline mole fractions were distinguished from pollution events by applying
133 the Robust Extraction of Baseline Signal (REBS) algorithm²⁵. This method has been
134 used several times for data extraction at the SDZ station^{3, 10, 11}. A local regression curve
135 was fitted using robustness weights for values above the baseline; data points outside
136 one-sigma around the current baseline were excluded. In this study, 60, 120 and 180
137 days of bandwidths for fitting were tested to obtain the best fit in the case of strong
138 mole fraction enhancement of some species, such as HCFC-22, during the three months
139 of June, July and August in 2021. After comparing typical species under three
140 conditions (Figure S6), 180 days was found to be the most suitable parameter for
141 obtaining the best fit. The fit converged after six iterations.

142 2.3 Emission estimate of halogenated gases

143 A tracer ratio method was applied to estimate the annual emissions of halogenated
144 gases from northern China. The ratios of atmospheric mole fraction enhancement
145 between halogenated gases and a tracer can be used to quantify the ratios of their mass
146 emission strengths when introducing their molecular weights²⁶ into the calculation, as
147 shown in Eq. (1). This method requires the tracer to have well understood emissions
148 and the same emission sources distribution as those of the target gas²⁷. The lifetimes
149 of species should be considerably greater than their transport time from source to SDZ
150^{26, 27}. The emissions can be calculated using Eq. (1) as

$$151 \quad E_X = E_{tracer} \cdot b \cdot (M_X/M_{tracer}), \quad (1)$$

152 where E is the emission of species, X represents the target halogenated gas, M is the
153 molecular weight, and b denotes the enhanced mole fraction ratio of a halogenated gas
154 (ΔX) to the tracer ($\Delta tracer$), i.e., $b = \Delta X/\Delta tracer$, which was obtained via linear
155 regression using an orthogonal distance regression method that considers the mole
156 fraction uncertainties of both the tracer (x-axis) and the halogenated gases (y-axis). The
157 values of b for each species are listed in Table S4.

158 The uncertainty σ (95% confidence interval) of the emission estimate is given by
159 error propagation as

$$160 \quad \sigma_{E_X} = E_X \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_b}{b}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{E_{tracer}}}{E_{tracer}}\right)^2}. \quad (2)$$

161 The most commonly used tracers in previous studies are CO²⁸⁻³¹ and HCFC-22^{6,}
162^{32, 33}. The source of CO from fossil and biofuel combustion is broadly co-located with

163 the emission sources of halogenated gases, which generally occurs in populated areas
164 ³⁴. Emissions of HCFC-22 from China have spatially extensive sources, and its
165 atmospheric mole fraction has significant statistical correlations with those of other
166 halogenated gases ^{33, 35}. Owing to their generally good correlations of enhanced mole
167 fractions (Figure 1), both CO and HCFC-22 were used as tracers in this study. The
168 emission of CO from northern China was $55 \pm 39 \text{ Tg yr}^{-1}$ during the study period, which
169 was obtained by the linear extrapolation of the CO emissions during 2019–2020
170 published by Zheng et al., (2021) ³⁶ using a bottom-up method. The emission of HCFC-
171 22 from northern China was 84 (69–100) Gg yr⁻¹ (2.5–97.5%, representing 2-sigma for
172 Gaussian uncertainties), which was obtained using a Lagrangian Particle Dispersion
173 Model, the UK Met Office Numerical Atmospheric-dispersion Modelling Environment
174 (NAME) ³⁷, and a hierarchical Bayesian inference methodology ^{38, 39}. Calculation
175 details of tracers' emissions and uncertainties are given in the supporting information
176 Section S3.1, which refer to An et al. (2021) ²¹. The emission uncertainties of the target
177 species were estimated using the error propagation, so the uncertainty of the tracer
178 HCFC-22 used for calculation was $\pm 15 \text{ Gg yr}^{-1}$ for northern China, approximating to
179 the 95% uncertainty interval (half of the difference between 97.5% and 2.5% value,
180 approximately 2-sigma for Gaussian distribution).

181

182 Figure 1. Correlations of the enhanced mole fraction of typical halogenated gases. Red numbers
 183 present the Pearson correlation coefficients (r) between two species; * indicates significant
 184 correlation between two compounds at the 0.05 level. The color and size of the dots represent the
 185 correlation strength, with larger dots and darker colors indicating stronger correlation.

186 The sensitivity of the observations obtained at the SDZ station to emissions from
 187 different regions of China in the study period was calculated through 30-day backward
 188 trajectories obtained using the NAME model. Figure 2 shows that measurements made
 189 at the SDZ station are sufficiently sensitive to emissions from northern China with high
 190 population densities in the provinces of Beijing, Tianjin, Hebei, Shanxi, Shaanxi, Inner
 191 Mongolia, Jilin, Liaoning, Shandong, Jiangsu, Anhui, and Henan. Thus, the observed
 192 atmospheric mole fractions of halogenated gases at the SDZ station could effectively
 193 reflect the emissions from northern China. The border of northern China area in this
 194 study is marked in dark gray in Figure 2.

195

196 Figure 2. Average sensitivity of the observations at the SDZ station to emissions of halogenated
 197 gases from October 2020 to September 2021.

198 3. Results and discussion

199 3.1 General features of mole fractions

200 The intercomparison results showed good consistency between the ODS5-pro
 201 system and the Medusa GC-MS system. The deviations of the annual mean mole
 202 fraction of most compounds between two systems were within $\pm 3\%$. The background
 203 and polluted mole fractions measured by ODS5-pro system were distinguished using
 204 the filter described in Section 2.2, and the mean background and polluted mole fractions
 205 as well as their standard deviations of 35 halogenated gases were determined, as listed
 206 in Table 1. CF_3Cl (CFC-11) was influenced by lab contamination and is thus not
 207 discussed herein. Overall, 25%–81% of all valid data were found to be close to
 208 background levels, depending on the gas. For most species which have been phased out
 209 by the Montreal Protocol (CFCs, halons, and CH_3CCl_3), 59%–81% of measurements
 210 were classified as background. However, CCl_4 exhibited a high frequency of pollution
 211 events, with only 40% of the measurements classified as background. The baseline data
 212 of all HCFCs in this study represented only 27%–29% of the measurements made,
 213 reflecting their continuous and strong emissions during the phase-down process in
 214 China. Similarly, 27%–33% of the measurement data was classified as background for
 215 HFC-32, HFC-125, HFC-134a, and HFC-227ea, which was the result of their increased
 216 emissions in recent years⁴. In addition, frequent pollution events occurred for some
 217 very short-lived halogenated gases (defined as species with an atmospheric lifetime of

218 less than six months ⁴⁰). These gases include CH₂Cl₂, CHCl₃ and C₂Cl₄ (PCE) with
 219 25%–31% of the measurements classified as background. Among all the halogenated
 220 gases measured, CH₂Cl₂ exhibited the lowest background data proportion.

221 **Table 1.** Background and polluted mole fractions of halogenated gases from October 2020 to
 222 September 2021 at the SDZ station.

Species	Molecular formula	Number of samples	Percentage of measurement categorized as background ^a	Background mole fraction			Polluted mole fraction			
				Mean (ppt)	S. D. ^b (ppt)	Change (ppt yr ⁻¹)	Mean (ppt)	S. D. ^b (ppt)	10% ^c (ppt)	90% ^c (ppt)
NF ₃	NF ₃	3147	43%	2.66	0.10	0.29 ± 0.01	4.56	2.64	2.88	7.55
SF ₆	SF ₆	3097	49%	10.7	0.36	0.86 ± 0.08	12.9	1.83	11.4	15.0
CF ₄	CF ₄	2984	43%	88.1	0.76	2.10 ± 0.13	91.5	2.55	89.1	94.7
PFC-116	C ₂ F ₆	3113	77%	5.09	0.21	0.19 ± 0.08	5.69	0.35	5.43	6.00
PFC-218	C ₃ F ₈	3120	77%	0.72	0.04	NL	0.83	0.05	0.79	0.90
PFC-318	C ₄ F ₈	3127	47%	1.95	0.05	0.09 ± 0.02	2.64	1.27	2.05	3.39
CFC-12	CF ₂ Cl ₂	3102	78%	498.9	2.04	-2.55 ± 0.53	503.9	1.89	502.0	506.0
CFC-13	CF ₃ Cl	3154	81%	3.25	0.14	NL	3.59	0.12	3.48	3.74
CFC-113	C ₂ F ₃ Cl ₃	3112	75%	69.1	0.69	-1.43 ± 0.22	71.3	1.74	69.9	73.2
CFC-114	C ₂ F ₄ Cl ₂	3137	77%	16.2	0.19	-0.30 ± 0.07	16.9	0.59	16.5	17.3
CFC-115	C ₂ F ₅ Cl	3146	75%	8.73	0.14	NL	9.35	0.66	8.98	10.0
HCFC-22	CHF ₂ Cl	3171	27%	260.6	3.57	NL	369.3	88.1	273.7	490.2
HCFC-141b	C ₂ H ₃ FCl ₂	3152	29%	26.4	0.35	NL	38.1	9.93	28.0	51.4
HCFC-142b	C ₂ H ₃ F ₂ Cl	3167	28%	23.3	0.45	NL	31.3	6.31	25.2	39.3
HFC-23	CHF ₃	2490	47%	35.2	0.55	1.42 ± 0.18	40.4	6.90	36.0	48.7
HFC-32	CH ₂ F ₂	3162	27%	31.7	1.41	4.90 ± 0.58	53.7	17.5	35.6	76.9
HFC-125	C ₂ HF ₅	3164	33%	38.4	1.06	3.13 ± 0.35	48.9	8.28	40.9	59.5
HFC-134a	C ₂ H ₂ F ₄	3043	29%	124.7	1.56	3.20 ± 0.93	151.4	22.5	129.8	177.2
HFC-143a	C ₂ H ₃ F ₃	3134	47%	28.3	0.63	1.47 ± 0.17	31.5	2.35	29.2	34.5
HFC-152a	C ₂ H ₄ F ₂	3163	45%	10.9	0.76	NL	16.1	4.79	12.4	20.6
HFC-227ea	C ₃ HF ₇	3151	32%	2.08	0.08	0.22 ± 0.03	3.41	2.10	2.29	4.73
HFC-236fa	C ₃ H ₂ F ₆	3135	75%	0.22	0.02	NL	0.29	0.04	0.26	0.33
HFC-245fa	C ₃ H ₃ F ₅	3162	48%	3.76	0.12	NL	4.91	1.12	4.05	6.14
HFC-365mfc	C ₄ H ₅ F ₅	3160	80%	1.33	0.06	NL	1.48	0.08	1.41	1.59
H-1211	CF ₂ BrCl	3154	59%	3.18	0.07	-0.06 ± 0.01	3.55	0.35	3.31	3.93
H-1301	CF ₃ Br	3154	75%	3.34	0.10	NL	3.77	0.73	3.51	4.03
H-2402	C ₂ F ₄ Br ₂	3029	77%	0.39	0.02	NL	0.44	0.04	0.41	0.48
CH ₃ CCl ₃	C ₂ H ₃ Cl ₃	2975	80%	1.34	0.08	-0.20 ± 0.03	1.50	0.09	1.38	1.61
CH ₃ Cl	CH ₃ Cl	3172	30%	533.7	26.4	NL	809.9	244.4	577.7	1138.9
CH ₂ Cl ₂	CH ₂ Cl ₂	3157	25%	77.1	6.81	NL	470.1	399.9	102.8	960.7
CHCl ₃	CHCl ₃	3171	30%	14.3	1.05	NL	64.3	57.1	19.4	131.2
CCl ₄	CCl ₄	2894	40%	76.1	0.92	NL	84.7	8.33	78.3	94.6
CH ₃ Br	CH ₃ Br	3097	44%	7.15	0.38	NL	10.8	2.73	8.18	14.1
SO ₂ F ₂	SO ₂ F ₂	3160	63%	2.79	0.08	0.07 ± 0.02	3.24	0.42	2.93	3.68
PCE	C ₂ Cl ₄	3169	31%	2.74	0.59	NL	13.0	9.59	4.24	24.3

- 223 a. These values represent the proportions of the background data volume to the raw data volume for
224 each species.
225 b. S. D. represents the standard deviations of the data.
226 c. 10% and 90% represent the 10th and 90th percentiles of polluted mole fractions for each species.
227 d. NL indicates no obvious changing trend for the species with $R^2 < 0.35$.

228 The observation working standards were traceable to the standards scales of the
229 Scripps Institution of Oceanography (SIO) ⁴¹. Therefore, the atmospheric baseline
230 obtained in this study was compared and verified with the data from the AGAGE station
231 Mace Head station in Ireland (53.3 °N, 9.9 °W), a typical observation station in the
232 Northern Hemisphere, during the same observation period of October 2020 to
233 September 2021 (Table S3). The annual mean background mole fractions of most
234 halogenated gases obtained at the SDZ station were consistent with the results observed
235 at the Mace Head station, with deviations within 5%. The background mole fractions
236 of some species (CH₂Cl₂, CH₃Cl, and PCE) at the SDZ station were much higher than
237 those observed at the Mace Head station (> 15%). This is mainly because that there are
238 always high regional increment at the SDZ station since frequent pollution events occur,
239 so that it is difficult to accurately extract the clean background conditions by the REBS
240 method.

241 The rates of annual baseline change were obtained via linear curve fitting of their
242 monthly average mole fractions. A degree of fitting (R^2) < 0.35 indicated no obvious
243 linear upward or downward trend (represented by NL in Table 1). The background mole
244 fractions of CFC-12, CFC-113, CFC-114, H-1211, and CH₃CCl₃ showed downward
245 trends, with annual average rates of -2.55 ± 0.53 , -1.43 ± 0.22 , -0.30 ± 0.07 , $-0.06 \pm$
246 0.01 , and -0.20 ± 0.03 ppt yr⁻¹, respectively. Most PFCs and HFCs showed substantial
247 upward trends. The background mole fractions of HCFCs fluctuated during 2020–2021
248 (Figure S8), which was different from the rapid increase of their background mole
249 fractions found in 2016 ⁴⁰.

250 **3.2 Interspecies correlations of halogenated gases**

251 Correlation analysis was conducted for the enhanced mole fraction (polluted mole
252 fraction minus the corresponding background mole fraction) of typical halogenated
253 gases (Figure 1). Low correlations were observed between CFCs and other species,
254 because the percentage of pollution events for major CFCs accounted for only 19%–
255 25% of the total data volume and their mole fraction enhancements were <10% of their
256 background (Table 1). However, strong correlations were observed between the

257 enhanced mole fractions of HCFCs and HFCs, reflecting their predominant productions,
258 consumptions, and large anthropogenic emissions in China. A comparably high
259 correlation was observed for HFC-32 and HFC-125 with a correlation coefficient (r) of
260 0.94 in this study. The result is different from the poor correlation reported by Li et al.
261 (2011)³² and Kim et al. (2010)⁶. They suggested that HFC-32 and HFC-125 were
262 emitted from fugitive leaks during industrial production. The strong correlation found
263 in this study confirms that the refrigerant R410A blend, which is 1:1 mixture of HFC-
264 32 and HFC-125 and the main substitute for HCFC-22, has been widely used in Chinese
265 residential air conditioners in the years since the previous studies⁴², and the
266 anthropogenic use of R410A has become the main emission source of HFC-32 and
267 HFC-125. In addition, HFC-143a widely exists in refrigerant blends of R404A and
268 R507A, leading to good correlations with HFC-32 and HFC-125 at $r = 0.70$ and $r =$
269 0.76 , respectively.

270 HFC-23 is mainly emitted as a byproduct from industrial production processes of
271 HCFC-22 in China. Similarly, PFC-318 is mainly produced and emitted during the
272 production of tetrafluoroethylene and other fluorochemicals with HCFC-22 as the raw
273 material^{43, 44}. A strong interspecies correlation of $r = 0.80$ was observed for HFC-23
274 and PFC-318, likely indicating their strong co-located emissions from HCFC-22-
275 related fluorine chemical industry.

276 Relatively high interspecies correlations of chloromethanes including CH_3Cl ,
277 CH_2Cl_2 , CHCl_3 , and CCl_4 with HCFCs and HFCs were also noted in Figure 1. In China,
278 chloromethanes are emitted during various industrial processes, including the feedstock
279 use for fluorochemical production and the widespread solvent use in populated and
280 industrialized areas^{21, 45, 46}. The relatively high correlations derived in this study could
281 be attributed to collocation of the emission sources of chloromethanes, HCFCs, and
282 HFCs in industrial regions.

283 **3.3 Emission estimates of HCFCs and F-gases**

284 The halogenated gases for which emissions were estimated herein are CF_4 , SF_6 ,
285 NF_3 , HCFC-22, HCFC-141b, HCFC-142b, HFC-23, HFC-32, HFC-125, HFC-134a,
286 HFC-143a, and HFC-152a. The global emissions of CF_4 in 2019 accounted for >80%
287 of all PFC emissions⁴⁷. Also, the CO_2 -eq emissions of HFC-32, HFC-125, HFC-134a,
288 HFC-143a, and HFC-152a accounted for >94% of the total CO_2 -eq emissions of
289 intentionally produced HFCs in China during 2011–2017⁴. Therefore, an almost

290 complete list of the four categories of F-gases (HFCs, PFCs, SF₆ and NF₃) as well as
 291 the major three HCFCs from northern China during 2020–2021 were estimated in this
 292 study and compared with their global emissions to determine the contribution of
 293 emissions from northern China to the global totals. Enhanced mole fractions of all
 294 species were significantly correlated with HCFC-22 and CO ($P < 0.05$), with $r > 0.43$
 295 (Figure 1). The emission of HCFC-22 from northern China estimated via the tracer ratio
 296 method with CO as a tracer was 70 ± 50 Gg yr⁻¹, which is comparable to the result
 297 derived using inverse modeling in this study within the uncertainty range. Overall, the
 298 emissions of halogenated gases estimated using CO as the tracer were 18% (HFC-23)
 299 to 39% (HFC-134a and NF₃) lower than those estimated using HCFC-22 as the tracer.
 300 This is probably because either the CO emission determined via linear extrapolation in
 301 2020–2021 was lower than the actual emission during this period, or the emission
 302 sources of CO were not as well co-located with the halogenated gases as HCFC-22.
 303 However, the estimated emissions by the two tracers were comparable with each other
 304 within the uncertainties. The emissions of HCFCs and F-gases discussed below refer to
 305 the results estimated using the tracer HCFC-22.

306 **Table 2.** Emissions of F-gases and HCFCs from northern China during 2020–2021, as determined
 307 using the tracer ratio method except when otherwise noted. Units are Gg yr⁻¹.

Species	Emissions	
	HCFC-22 as a tracer	CO as a tracer
CF ₄	1.6 ± 0.4	1.1 ± 0.8
NF ₃	1.2 ± 0.3	0.7 ± 0.5
SF ₆	1.8 ± 0.4	1.5 ± 1.1
HCFC-22	84 (69–100) ^a	70 ± 50
HCFC-141b	12 ± 2	8.6 ± 6.2
HCFC-142b	6.1 ± 1.2	3.8 ± 2.8
HFC-23	3.2 ± 0.9	2.6 ± 2.0
HFC-32	8.8 ± 1.7	6.5 ± 4.7
HFC-125	8.9 ± 1.8	6.4 ± 4.7
HFC-134a	18 ± 4	11 ± 8
HFC-143a	1.4 ± 0.3	1.0 ± 0.7
HFC-152a	2.0 ± 0.5	1.6 ± 1.2

308 a. Emission of HCFC-22 obtained via inverse modeling.

309 b. All uncertainties during the emission estimates are at 95% confidence interval.

310 Considering that there were few studies on the emission estimates of halogenated
 311 gases from northern China specifically, this study scaled down the emissions from

312 China published by other studies to obtain the emissions from northern China. Then,
313 the emissions estimated for northern China in this study could be compared with those
314 of other studies. The scaling down ratio was equal to the proportion of HCFC-22
315 emissions from northern China to the emissions from China, both of which were
316 estimated by the NAME model and a hierarchical Bayesian inference methodology (see
317 supporting information S3.1). The posteriori emission of HCFC-22 from China during
318 2020–2021 was 171 (128–217) Gg yr⁻¹ (2.5–97.5%, representing 2-sigma for Gaussian
319 uncertainties), and the proportion of the emissions from northern China was 49%, so
320 that the emissions of halogenated gases from northern China in other studies discussed
321 below and shown in Figure 3, Figure 4, and Figure 5 were calculated by multiplying
322 their published emissions from China by the ratio 49%.

323 **3.3.1 CF₄, NF₃, and SF₆**

324 The emissions of CF₄ and NF₃ are primarily thought to be from industry-specific
325 point sources. As a strong greenhouse gas (GWP_{100yr} = 6630), CF₄ is the most
326 chemically simple and the abundant atmospheric PFC, with a known longest lifetime
327 of 50,000 years⁴⁰. A renewed steady increase in the global mole fraction growth rate of
328 0.9 ppt yr⁻¹ was found for CF₄; the background mole fraction of which reached 85.5
329 ppt in 2019⁴⁷. The increase in the CF₄ mole fraction is mainly attributed to the emissions
330 from the aluminum production, semiconductor manufacturing, and rare-earth metal
331 production industries⁹. NF₃ is another important GHG with a GWP_{100yr} of 15750,
332 originating mainly from semiconductor, magnesium, and aluminum manufacturing
333 industries worldwide⁴⁸. The baseline mole fraction growth rate of NF₃ has been
334 accelerating since 1990 with an annual growth rate of >10%¹. Accurate industrial
335 production and consumption information of CF₄ and NF₃ is difficult to obtain. For
336 example, emissions from the aluminum production industry are considerably affected
337 by manufacturing conditions; thus, the emission factors cannot be accurately estimated.
338 Moreover, emission-related information and emission-reduction efficiency in the
339 electronics industry are not reported⁹. This creates difficulty in estimating their bottom-
340 up inventories; the estimation requires the use of activity data and emission factors.
341 Moreover, the accuracy of emissions obtained via inverse modeling is limited by the a
342 priori emission distribution, representativeness of the observations, and measurement
343 accuracy. Therefore, few studies have estimated CF₄ and NF₃ emissions from China,
344 with large gaps present in the reported emissions^{3, 9, 49, 50}, and no studies focused on the

345 emissions of CF₄ and NF₃ from northern China. An inverse modeling result ⁹ showed
346 that China had the largest CF₄ emissions among East Asian countries during 2008–2015
347 ⁹. Between 2008 and 2015, the CF₄ emissions from China stabilized at 2–6 Gg yr⁻¹,
348 which was more than twice the range of 1–3 Gg yr⁻¹ reported by the Emission Database
349 for Global Atmospheric Research (EDGAR) v6.0 ⁵⁰. The values reported in 2017–2019
350 increased by 29% over those reported in 2012–2014 ⁴⁹. Here, the CF₄ emissions from
351 northern China during 2020–2021 were estimated as 1.6 ± 0.4 Gg yr⁻¹. The NF₃
352 emission from China derived via inverse modeling (0.36–1.08 Gg yr⁻¹) ⁹ during 2014–
353 2015 was also considerably higher than the bottom-up estimate of 0.03 Gg yr⁻¹ ⁵⁰.
354 During 2020–2021, NF₃ emissions from northern China in this study reached 1.2 ± 0.3
355 Gg yr⁻¹, which was more than twice the scaled-down emission reported for 2014–2015
356 ⁹.

357 SF₆ is considered as the most potent GHG, with a GWP_{100yr} of 23500 ⁴⁰. It is mainly
358 used by the electronics industry for high-voltage equipment, and small amounts are
359 used as a protective gas during the metal smelting process and as an etchant in the
360 electronics industry ⁸. SF₆ from the above sources leaks into the atmosphere during
361 production, maintenance, and recharging, resulting in enhanced ambient mole fractions.
362 Emissions from the electrical equipment industry account for 70% of the total SF₆
363 emissions in China ⁵¹, which has been increasing considerably in recent years with
364 greater demands for electricity. According to the inverse modeling results reported by
365 Simmonds et al. (2020) ⁸, SF₆ emissions from China increased from 1.4 Gg yr⁻¹ in 2007
366 to 3.2 Gg yr⁻¹ in 2018, representing a 130% increase, and its contribution to global
367 emissions increased from 0.9% in 1990 ⁵¹ to 36% in 2018 ⁸. Linear extrapolation of the
368 scaled-down abovementioned result indicated that SF₆ emissions from northern China
369 would have reached 1.8 Gg yr⁻¹ in 2020, which is consistent with the emission
370 estimated herein as 1.8 ± 0.4 Gg yr⁻¹. The published bottom-up emission inventories of
371 SF₆ in the electronics industry ⁸ were always higher than the results of both this study
372 and the top-down study of Simmonds et al. (2020) ⁸ after 2013.

373

374

375 Figure 3. Emissions of CF₄, NF₃, and SF₆ derived using the tracer ratio method in this study
 376 compared with the reported estimates for northern China^{3, 6-9, 32, 49-51}.

377 3.3.2 HCFCs

378 The main HCFCs produced and consumed in China are HCFC-22, HCFC-141b,
 379 and HCFC-142b. They are commonly used as refrigerants in air conditioners and
 380 blowing agents for insulation materials⁵². Because China began to formally phase down
 381 HCFCs in 2013, some studies have reported a slowed down increase or even a decrease
 382 in HCFCs emissions after 2013⁵³. This study estimated the emissions of these HCFCs
 383 from northern China as 84 (69–100) Gg yr⁻¹ for HCFC-22, 12 ± 2 Gg yr⁻¹ for HCFC-
 384 141b, and 6.1 ± 1.2 Gg yr⁻¹ for HCFC-142b, respectively. The emissions from northern
 385 China estimated herein are close to the scaled-down emissions for 2020 predicted by
 386 Fang et al. (2018)⁵⁴, as shown in Figure 4. HCFC-22 emissions exhibited minor
 387 fluctuations since 2013, whereas the emissions of HCFC-141b and HCFC-142b
 388 considerably increased in 2020–2021 compared with the values reported before 2019.
 389 For example, the emissions of HCFC-141b and HCFC-142b from northern China in
 390 2020–2021 were 120% and 98% higher than those in 2019, respectively, as estimated
 391 by Yi et al. (2021)¹³. Although the reason for the increase is not clear, it may be
 392 attributed to the large amount of bank emissions that occur when an appliance reaches
 393 the end of its service life or the unreported HCFC production for dispersive uses⁵⁶.
 394 Thus, it is necessary to further inspect and verify the actual productions and

395 consumptions of HCFCs to explain the emissions increase.

396

397

398 Figure 4. Emissions of HCFCs derived using the tracer ratio method in this study compared with
399 the reported estimates for northern China ^{6, 13, 22, 26, 32, 53, 54, 57-62}.

400 3.3.3 HFCs

401 HFC-32, HFC-125, HFC-134a, and HFC-143a are primarily used as refrigerants
402 in China. The emissions from northern China of HFC-134a, which is used as a
403 refrigerant in mobile air conditioners, showed different changing trends between studies
404 using different estimation methods (Figure 5). The bottom-up estimates showed steady
405 increases during 2008–2019, while top-down estimates indicated peak emissions
406 around 2015 followed by a decrease until 2018. The estimated emissions of HFC-134a
407 in 2020–2021 using HCFC-22 and CO as a tracer in this study were 18 ± 4 and 11 ± 8
408 Gg yr^{-1} , which were comparable to the bottom-up and top-down estimates according to
409 their changing trends, respectively. HFC-32 and HFC-125 are equally mixed in the
410 refrigerant R410A, which is used to replace HCFC-22 in room air conditioners. The
411 emissions of HFC-32 and HFC-125 from northern China were $8.8 \pm 1.7 \text{ Gg yr}^{-1}$ and
412 $8.9 \pm 1.8 \text{ Gg yr}^{-1}$, respectively, in a 1:1 proportion. If the scaled-down emissions
413 continue to increase after 2017 according to the growth rates reported by Yao et al.
414 (2019) ⁴, the results reported herein are within a reasonable range but are lower than

415 those estimated by Li et al. (2019) ⁶³ and Fang et al. (2018) ⁵⁴, based on bottom-up
416 methods. This can be attributed to an overestimation of their historical productions and
417 consumptions or the non-linear growth of emissions resulting from their decreasing
418 consumption in recent years. The emissions of HFC-143a during 2020–2021 from
419 northern China were small, at $1.4 \pm 0.3 \text{ Gg yr}^{-1}$. These values do not represent an
420 increase in HFC-143a emission compared with the inverse modeled emissions before
421 2017 ⁴; however, they are considerably higher than the bottom-up estimate of Li et al.
422 (2019) ⁶³. The activity data and emission factor of HFC-143a may need further
423 verification. Although the production of HFC-152a is large in China, it is mainly used
424 for export or as a raw material ⁶⁴. The emissions of HFC-152a from northern China
425 during 2020–2021 were $2.0 \pm 0.5 \text{ Gg yr}^{-1}$, and remained stable. These results are
426 considerably lower than the emissions estimated by Fang et al. (2018) ⁵⁴ but are close
427 to the inversion result reported by Yao et al. (2019) ⁴. Byproducts from the production
428 of HCFC-22 are supposed to be the main sources of HFC-23 emission, which in 2020–
429 2021 was estimated as $3.2 \pm 0.9 \text{ Gg yr}^{-1}$ from northern China. This result partly explains
430 the global discrepancies of 13.5 Gg yr^{-1} in 2018 between the expected and estimated
431 emissions reported by Stanley et al. (2020) ⁶⁵.

432 Discrepancies between the emission estimates from different studies may be in
433 part due to observation networks of halogenated gases having an incomplete coverage
434 in terms of their sensitivity to emissions. The ODS5-pro system used in this study is
435 beneficial for the establishment and extension of the observation network and will help
436 to reduce uncertainty in emission estimates in future research.

437

438

439 Figure 5. Emissions of HFCs derived using the tracer ratio method in this study compared with the
 440 reported estimates for northern China^{3-6, 9, 13, 32, 50, 54, 57-59, 63, 66-69}.

441 **3.3.4 CO₂-eq emission proportions of each species and their contributions to**
 442 **global emissions**

443 In addition to CH₄ and N₂O, F-gases represent a large category of anthropogenic
 444 non-CO₂ GHGs specified by the UNFCCC. The global CO₂-eq emissions of F-gases

445 reached 1.4 ± 0.41 Gt in 2019, representing an increase of 250% compared with those
 446 in 1990⁷⁰. Herein, the total CO₂-eq emissions of CF₄, NF₃, SF₆, and major HFCs from
 447 northern China during 2020–2021 reached 181 ± 18 Tg yr⁻¹, equivalent to 13% of the
 448 global F-gases CO₂-eq emissions in 2020⁷⁰. Among all F-gases estimated, in terms of
 449 CO₂-eq emissions, SF₆ contributed the most to global warming (24%), followed by
 450 HFC-23 (22%), HFC-125 (17%), HFC-134a (13%), NF₃ (10%), CF₄ (5.9%), HFC-143a
 451 (3.9%), HFC-32 (3.4%), and HFC-152a (0.2%). If the emissions of HCFCs are
 452 considered, HCFC-22 contributed nearly half (42%) of the CO₂-eq emissions of F-gases
 453 and HCFCs combined owing to its substantial physical emissions (Figure 6). Reduction
 454 of HCFC emissions will contribute to the recovery of the ozone layer and play a positive
 455 role in climate change mitigation.
 456

457
 458 Figure 6. The CO₂-eq emission proportion of each species in (a) F-gases and in (b) both F-gases
 459 and HCFCs.

460 Table S2 shows the emission contributions of each F-gas and HCFC from northern
 461 China with respect to the global values. The proportions of NF₃, SF₆, and HCFCs from
 462 northern China alone were high at 20–40%, indicating that emissions from the whole
 463 area of China of these species may represent up to half of the global emission sources.
 464 Therefore, the emission mitigation of NF₃, SF₆, and HCFCs in China will have an
 465 important impact on the global emission reduction process. Emissions of intentionally
 466 produced HFCs (HFCs in this study except HFC-23) from northern China accounted
 467 for a low proportion of global emissions (<15%). HFC-152a had the smallest
 468 contribution (<4%) to global emissions among all species owing to its main usage for
 469 export as a raw material in China. However, the contribution proportion of HFC-23 was
 470 19%, which was relatively higher than other intentionally produced HFCs.

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486 **5. Associated content**

487 **Supporting Information**

488 The Supporting Information is available free of charge online. The instrument
489 description including the development of ODS5-pro system, the quantitative method
490 and evaluation index, the instrument performance, and the intercomparison with
491 Medusa GC-MS system are described in Section S1. The baseline extraction result for
492 different bandwidths of REBS method is shown in Section S2. The emission data
493 sources and uncertainties of the tracer compounds are presented in Section S3. Emission
494 proportions of halogenated gases from northern China to the global emissions are given
495 in Section S4. Comparison of annual average background mole fractions observed at
496 the SDZ station and the Mace Head station is given in Table S3. The regression slope
497 and uncertainty between target species and tracers are listed in Table S4. The monthly
498 mean background mole fractions of HCFCs are shown in Figure S8.

499

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